

Digital Research Infrastructure
for the Arts and Humanities

ANNUAL REPORT 2019

DARIAH ERIC:
A research
infrastructure to
enhance and support
digitally enabled
research and teaching
across the Arts and
Humanities.

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Foreword

We are pleased to present you with this Annual Report for the year 2019. More than at any other point in our annual calendar, the creation of this document each year gives us a chance to reflect on our achievements as an infrastructure, and, in particular, on the question of how we have made a difference for researchers in Europe.

For the first time in 2019, we were able to say that the delivery of this impact is being guided by a formally validated, long-term vision, as enshrined in our newly released [Strategic Plan](#). This document lends us renewed confidence in our actions, as we know that we have an approved and agreed mandate to take us through the next seven years. In addition, the conclusion of the DESIR project has enabled us to reflect on the many faceted challenges of ensuring the sustainability of our activities, and inspired us to continue to explore and innovate for and with our community.

The year was, as ever, full of events, small and large, local and national. Of particular note were of course our largest ever Annual Event, held in the beautiful city of Warsaw, and the final DARIAH beyond Europe event in Canberra, but these were just two of the many opportunities we have been able to facilitate to share knowledge and advance research for individuals and institutions. We will also look back on 2019 as a watershed year for our commitment to Open Science, as our many projects, collaborations and services began to take a more coherent and coordinated shape. In addition, the tools, publications and events fostered by our Theme and Working Group funding mechanisms demonstrate the real difference that a well-managed investment, even a relatively small one, in our amazing network can make.

We are pleased to see that this impact is felt and valued, not just by our existing researcher base and partner network, but by the many new collaborators, cooperating partners, and indeed our two new member countries, Bulgaria and the Czech Republic. We look forward to a long and fruitful collaboration with these two new members of our distributed network of infrastructure providers.

It is already clear at the time of writing this foreword that 2020 will bring us unprecedented challenges: next year's Annual Report will surely look very different from this one, just as the world seems to have changed utterly in a few short weeks. But we have enormous faith in the DARIAH structure, ethos, team and community that we, as an organisation, will use this moment to find opportunities to dig in and deepen our support for research and researchers, now and into the future. Our new Mission Statement sets us a clear and strong mandate to "empower research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge about culture and society". The challenges of 2020 will be an opportunity to find new ways to fulfil this commitment, playing our part to ensure that research in Europe can continue to thrive, even under adverse conditions. We look forward to sharing the results of this commitment with you next year.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Jennifer Edmond'.

Jennifer Edmond
President of the Board of Directors

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Jacques Dubucs'.

Jacques Dubucs
President of the General Assembly

DARIAH in a Nutshell

The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH) enhances and supports digitally-enabled research and teaching across the arts and humanities. DARIAH is a research infrastructure of people, expertise, information, knowledge, content, methods, tools and technologies from its member countries. It develops, maintains and operates an infrastructure that sustains researchers in building, analysing and interpreting digital resources. By working with communities of practice, DARIAH brings together individual state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities and scales their results to a European level, enabling the transition to Open Science, and beyond to Open Innovation. It preserves, provides access to, and disseminates research that stems from these collaborations and ensures that best practices, methodological and technical standards are followed.

DARIAH was established as a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in August 2014. In 2019, the consortium had 19 Members and 26 Cooperating Partners across 8 non-member countries. DARIAH integrates digital arts and humanities research and activities from across Europe, enabling transnational and transdisciplinary approaches.

In particular, it provides value to its members and stakeholders through the validation and sharing of data, services and tools; by providing training and education opportunities; by enabling 'bottom up' organisation around emerging research needs; and through the exercise of foresight and policy engagement. Through these activities, DARIAH promotes the further development of research methods in the arts and humanities, documenting the state-of-the-art, supporting the preservation and curation of research data with a focus on particular challenges including diversity, provenance, multimedia collections and granularity, and acting as a coordinator and integrator for a diverse community of practice.

The consortium supports the sustainable development of digitally-enabled research in the arts and humanities by building services for researchers working with ICT-based methods. It helps them to further advance their research and ensures the long-term accessibility of their work, thus directly contributing to the understanding of the cultural, economical, social and political life in Europe and beyond. In addition, it offers teaching material as well as teaching opportunities to develop digital research skills.

DARIAH is at the forefront of a changing knowledge discovery market and possesses significant strength in this field through its partners. DARIAH also demonstrates how traditional humanities research skills play a prominent role in the digital age, and how such skills can be deployed in a digital economy setting. The DARIAH vision is that humanities researchers will be able to assess the impact of technology on their work in an informed manner, access the data, tools, services, knowledge and networks they need seamlessly and in contextually rich virtual and human environments and produce excellent, digitally-enabled scholarship that is reusable, visible and sustainable.

Activity Highlights 2019

1 Start of the Horizon 2020 Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud project

Coordinated by CESSDA ERIC, the project aims to provide a full-fledged Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) where data, tools and training material are available and accessible for SSH users. DARIAH's ambitious role in the project is to develop the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace (the SSH Open Marketplace) under Work Package 7. First prototypes of the SSH Open Marketplace will be released in June 2020.

1

January

February

3 DARIAH at the National Library of Australia

In March, DARIAH organised the third DARIAH beyond Europe event in conjunction with the second annual Humanities, Arts and Culture Data Summit at the National Library of Australia in Canberra. The event was a rich thinking opportunity allowing more than 100 participants to confront their research perspectives and to exchange knowledge on infrastructures in Australia and Europe. This landmark event was held in collaboration with the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) and the Australian Academy of the Humanities (AAH). (See page 16)

3

March

April

2

2 DARIAH joins the ERIC Forum Implementation Project

Co-funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 programme, the aim of the ERIC Forum Implementation Project is to bring together the 20 established ERICs and 3 ERICs in preparation in order to strengthen their coordination and enhance their collaborations. The strategic approach of the ERIC Forum will contribute to address critical challenges and develop best practices.

4

4 DARIAH publishes its first Strategic Plan for 2019-2026

This strategy, which will guide DARIAH's activities and operation over the next years, stands upon the four pillars of: building the Marketplace, approaching training and education strategically, deepening the connection to DARIAH's communities and strengthening DARIAH's voice in policy and advocacy.

Record attendance at DARIAH Annual Event 2019

With more than 250 participants, the DARIAH Annual Event 2019 was the biggest event ever organised by the infrastructure. Hosted by DARIAH-Poland, it took place on 15-17 May at Warsaw University Library. The topic was Humanities Data, inviting keynotes and presentations to reflect on the term 'data', to discuss the type and amount of data that humanists collect and to address their data needs. (See page 14)

5

May

September

October

November

6

Publication of the DARIAH Working Groups Policy Statement

The DARIAH Working Groups Policy Statement is an important guide on the role of Working Groups, the framework in which they function, their context and lifecycle. It will give current and future Working Groups a firm basis to maximise the value of their interactions internally and to the DARIAH community as a whole.

DARIAH Working Groups Funding Scheme 2019

In 2019, DARIAH launched its second Working Groups funding scheme call. With a total amount of 25,000 €, five Working Groups have been selected for funding to implement, develop or sustain small-scale projects and innovative ideas. (See page 26)

8

DARIAH expands its Membership

DARIAH was happy to welcome Czech Republic as its new member in November. Earlier in the year, DARIAH also welcomed Bulgaria, reaching thus the number of 19 full members. With two new members in 2019, DARIAH also expanded its membership welcoming new cooperating partners in four countries: United Kingdom (University of Lancaster and University of Exeter), Sweden (Uppsala University), Slovakia (Slovak Academy of Sciences) and Switzerland (SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics).

9

DARIAH welcomes a new Working Group on Bibliographical Data

Chaired by Vojtěch Malínek from the Institute of Czech Literature of the Czech Academy of Sciences and Dr. Tomasz Umerle from the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences, the BiblioData Working Group aims to foster cooperation between all the parties involved in the bibliographical data life cycle, such as data producers, curators, researchers and theorists of documentation and bibliography, leading to a greater and more diverse research use of bibliographical data in the humanities. (See page 7)

7

1. Nurturing and Expanding DARIAH's Network

a. The DARIAH Community in 2019

The very nature of the DARIAH community makes any attempt to define its scope and perimeter at least complex. If the core of the organisation is composed of a handful of persons, its ramifications spread to an ever-widening community of individuals and institutions that organise themselves at both national and European levels. Furthermore, the nature of the DARIAH "user" adds further complexity to the architecture of the community: most DARIAH users are at the same time contributing to the infrastructure, through their participation in Working Groups and projects, through their generation of in kind contributions and local influence.

The arts and humanities research community in Europe has been estimated to encompass more than 500,000 individuals in research, teaching and cultural heritage. Every one of these is a potential DARIAH user, but the distributed nature of our organisation means that often, there is one or more degrees of separation from the central offices. However, as illustrated with the figure below, DARIAH's sphere of influence is large and each of these layers contributes to its unique strength.

b. Working Groups

DARIAH in 2019 counts 23 Working Groups. As one of the DARIAH strategic pillars, the Working Groups remain at the heart of the infrastructure, representing the research communities, diverse research topics, methodologies and innovation in the arts and humanities. Recognising their importance and centrality for DARIAH, over the year we aimed in strengthening the communication and collaboration among the Working Groups, in a way that also supports the growth of the research communities. To achieve this, we launched the DARIAH Working Groups Community Calls.

Community Calls functioned as 'virtual' continuation of the face to face Working Groups meetings aimed in building an active community by facilitating the exchange between the Working Groups on topics that they have in common or that could lay further ground for collaboration. For this reason, the moderation was kept to a minimum, to allow as much as possible ideas exchange and open discussion.

Three Community Calls were organised in 2019, facilitated by Working Group chairs. Since their launch, there has been an increase of spontaneous inter-Working Group collaborations. Working Groups realised that they are working on similar research questions, even if from different angles, and the richness brought by a different perspective can only enrich their own research field.

BIBLIO DATA WORKING GROUP

2019 saw also the start of a new Working Group: the **Working Group on Bibliographical Data**. Its focus is to foster cooperation between all the parties involved in the bibliographical data life cycle (especially data producers, managers/curators, researchers, and theorists of documentation and bibliography), in order to contribute to the greater and more diverse research use of bibliographical data in the humanities.

Although bibliographical data is central to the humanities, and comprises of numerous services, tools, resources and interested researchers, there are no comprehensive initiatives aimed at addressing the issues of bibliographical data from the perspective of digital humanities and data-driven research.

The BiblioData Working Group is a bottom-up attempt to bring together those different actors and assets in order to build a larger framework for bibliographical data research, and address the main issues that the community is facing.

Image by Encre Noire Corporate, CC BY

Focus on the Bibliographical Data Working Group

The BiblioData Working Group is co-chaired by Tomasz Umerle (Institute for Literary Research of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Poznan) and Vojtěch Malínek (Institute of Czech Literature, Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague).

Tomasz works at the Institute of Literary Research of the Polish Academy as a Deputy Director of the Current Bibliography Department, and as Assistant Professor, interested mostly in documentation studies, bibliographical data, and empirical literary studies.

Vojtěch works at the Institute of Czech literature as Czech Literary Bibliography Research Infrastructure Coordinator. His main interest in bibliographical study is in data processes, data management and data-driven research.

“Our Working Group is very heterogeneous, especially if we think of our backgrounds and academic interests: some of us are academics, others work in libraries or research centers as data managers, curators, or as IT specialists. Integration of these communities is a task that demands support from consortiums like DARIAH ERIC.

“Our research interests and backgrounds vary from bibliometrics, cultural analytics, book history, library and information science, data analytics, software development and digital humanities” explains Tomasz “and this also reflects on the aims of our Working Group: on the one hand, we want to map the European bibliographical landscape and provide best practices to our fellow researchers. On the other hand, we want to connect experts in this field by establishing a platform for mutual discussion, by organising events, but also to provide a meeting point for writing funding proposals and joint international projects”.

“DARIAH ERIC is a right environment for such an initiative, as it gives us the chance to extend our network (as expressed in the strategic documents such as the [DARIAH Strategic Action Plan](#)) and to sharpen our external communications” adds Vojtěch. “2020 will be a busy year for our group. We are planning our first event, a Working Group booksprint in early 2020, whose aim is that of working on a report on bibliodata landscape in the humanities. With this report we would like to reach a diverse and dispersed community of researchers and curators, and provide a new channel for discussing bibliodata as a shared topic, and an issue central to any humanities RI discussions”.

Tomasz Umerle

Vojtěch Malínek

c. DARIAH at the National Level

The richness and dynamism of the DARIAH consortium lies first and foremost in the diversity and plurality of its member countries. It is they who every day through their actions, projects and influence make DARIAH a key infrastructure in the field of the arts and humanities. National Members meet and work through the National Coordinators Committee (NCC) that gathers regularly either virtually or face to face to reflect on and coordinate the actions of its members. In 2019, they worked more specifically on validating the Strategic Plan of DARIAH for the next seven years, which is to be reflected also on their national roadmaps, welcoming in their discussions the six countries preparing for accession under the DESIR project.

The most important outcome of 2019 was the successful application of Bulgaria and Czech Republic to join DARIAH in May and November respectively. The application

of these two countries was validated by the General Assembly who warmly welcomed the two new member countries in the infrastructure. DARIAH, counting now 19 full members, also expanded its membership to countries who are represented within DARIAH by institutions that participate as Cooperating Partners. In 2019, DARIAH had a total of 26 Cooperating Partners, welcoming 5 new ones: United Kingdom (University of Lancaster and University of Exeter), Sweden (Uppsala University), Slovakia (Slovak Academy of Sciences) and Switzerland (SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics).

Both Bulgaria and the Czech Republic joined DARIAH with ambitious national roadmaps and strong national consortia. Their membership opened up new opportunities for further collaborations across Europe, gaining new cultural perspectives and strengthening ties on behalf of the arts and humanities in a technologically evolving knowledge society. Next, we feature their stories.

Focus on Czech Republic

Deputy director for research, development and technology at the Library of Czech Academy of Sciences (Prague, Czech Republic), Martin Lhoták is the National Coordinator of the Czech DARIAH consortium. Martin was coordinating the accession process of the Czech Republic to DARIAH ERIC in the frame of the DESIR project. He currently participates in digital humanities projects focusing mainly on the development of new tools for the infrastructure while he is also actively involved in the open access movement, initiating the Open Access Policy of the Czech Academy of Sciences.

Martin Lhoták

Could you introduce us to the role and work of the Czech DARIAH consortium (LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ)?

The LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ RI brings together the most prominent institutions covering many disciplines with relation to digital humanities: from literature and oral history to visual art (2D and 3D), archaeology and Egyptology. We consider, as a particular strength of the Czech DARIAH partners, the libraries, the inclusion of other national heritage institutions, and the technology strength of the three technology-oriented partners (Charles University, University of West Bohemia and Masaryk University) in the areas of Natural Language Processing, Artificial Intelligence and multimedia processing. In addition, the substantial experience of the existing Charles University team in running the CLARIN certified language resources repository will be extended to other types of research data coming from the digital humanities and arts.

The project partners have all subscribed to the idea of digital data preparation and open sharing, development of new tools and common standards to provide information about their collections to the research community, and to the idea of mutual cooperation within the country and beyond, all within the DARIAH network.

Thanks to the full membership of the Czech Republic in DARIAH, we are expecting positive impact that will lead to strengthening and growing the infrastructure for digital humanities in the Czech Republic as well as the research in digital humanities. By entering this wide and well-established European research community, we gain access to many experts in the field (especially by joining selected Working Groups), as well as the possibility to use the research infrastructure – tools and services – which is available to the DARIAH ERIC members. These facts enable enhancement and growth in the area of research in digital humanities in the Czech Republic and it will contribute to the creation of research results on the highest international level.

What would you consider to be the highlights of 2019 for LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ?

One of the main goals in 2019 was to successfully apply for full DARIAH membership. Our official application was submitted to the DARIAH Board of Directors in June, signed by the Minister of Education, Youth and Sport (MEYS) Robert Plaga. After introducing the Czech DARIAH consortium at the DARIAH General Assembly in November, our application was unanimously approved, joining thus officially the ERIC. Another breakthrough was our inclusion in the Czech Republic's Research Infrastructure Roadmap. This ensures national funding from 2019 till 2022, to hold and develop the research infrastructure.

But 2019 was more than that:

1. At the end of June 2019, the Central European DARIAH Hub (CEH), which comprises of institutions from Austria, Poland, Slovakia, Hungary and the Czech Republic, organised a first workshop on Natural Language Processing and Corpus Linguistics. This workshop is part of a wider project and series of workshops by the Central European Hub which was approved and supported from Visegrad Funds.
2. A series of three autumn tutorials was also organised. The first two tutorials were introducing services of LINDAT/CLARIAH-CZ members while the third one focused on introduction to TEI and it was provided by colleagues from Karl-Franzes-Universität in Graz, Austria, with support from the DESIR project.
3. Aiming to enable search through all data and services via one main point, one of the preparatory activities in 2019 was to collect and analyse detailed description of metadata and data from every partner in order to select a set of metadata for common search and database.

Focus on Bulgaria

Dimitar Iliev and Kiril Simov are the National Coordinators of the Bulgarian DARIAH consortium called CLaDA-BG (CLARIN and DARIAH in Bulgaria). With a background in Ancient Greek Linguistics, Computer Linguistics and Humanities Computing, Dimitar is the principal investigator of the Telamon digital collection of Greek inscriptions from Bulgaria and is currently involved in several initiatives such as the Time Machine Organisation.

Kiril is Professor at the Linguistic Modelling Department, IICT of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences. His research interests are in the areas of Natural Language Processing, Language Resources, Knowledge Graphs and Ontologies. He has led European projects in the areas of language and semantic technologies and a number of projects supported by the German foundation Volkswagen.

Could you introduce us to the role and work of CLaDA-BG?

CLaDA-BG is a national research e-infrastructure of 15 research and educational institutions, based in Bulgaria. Several of the technological partners in the consortium are currently building a network of data centres for the storage, management, processing and publishing of datasets and online collections of linguistic and cultural content. The work in CLaDA-BG is also dedicated to the development of tools and methods, the introduction and promotion of good research practices in NLP and DH, as well as the creation of teaching materials for the Bulgarian and international research community. The content providers in the consortium are involved in the process of selection and preparation of well-formed sets of quality data in the fields of languages and linguistics, cultural heritage and other areas of humanities. They are also engaged in further promoting the digital methods and instruments applied in CLaDA-BG.

Our mission is to establish good practices of interdisciplinary collaboration between scholars and scientists from different fields with the goal of creating collections, tools and a knowledge graph to model and represent linguistic content and cultural and historical heritage. We aim to spread these good practices among the scholarly and scientific communities in Bulgaria, including major and local GLAM institutions and involve as many researchers as possible in the application and development of our instruments.

The accumulation of knowledge from different sources will enable us to contribute to our society as well as to the international communities of CLARIN and DARIAH with open and accessible collections and datasets of relevant linguistic and cultural content, accompanied by the tools and the documentation for their usage and modification.

What would you consider to be the highlights of 2019 for CLaDA-BG?

- First meeting of the International Advisory Board of the CLaDA-BG consortium organised in July 2019 in Sofia. The experts in the advisory panel gave their feedback in several directions: key performance indicators, data from Bulgarian resources due to be integrated in European and/or international platforms and databases for better visibility, extension of the international contacts through practical presentations of the results and datasets of the consortium.
- **PARTHENOS Workshop** in October 2019: The objective of the workshop was to foster collaboration among researchers in social sciences and humanities in Central and Eastern Europe, on the one hand, and the research communities in these fields in CLARIN and EU-funded project PARTHENOS, on the other.
- Launch of an international Working Group on digital sigillography (XML encoding and publishing of ancient and mediaeval seals) in a series of meetings in Bulgaria (October 2019) and Germany (December 2019) and production of a first version of integrated language resources with the corpus of the Bulgarian Wikipedia. This work aims to: (1) train an extended set of processing modules that perform multiple tasks simultaneously in an end-to-end training fashion, and (2) provide contextualisation to the senses and facts through the mapping of the relations in the text with the encyclopaedic information. The latter is considered a very important step for successfully using the language processing for information extraction from textual descriptions of cultural and historical objects.

d. DARIAH Collaborations

i. Connecting Dots for Open Science

At DARIAH, we do more than just advocate collaborative knowledge creation practices: we live them, placing them at the heart of our own day-to-day work, harnessing the benefits we can profit from by working together. In 2019, we put special emphasis on situating DARIAH within the colourful network of European and global Open Science actors, aligning strategies with them, and tuning the outputs of these networks toward a better alignment with arts and humanities research practices. The chart below gives an overview of our most important collaborations in this respect and the milestones we achieved together in 2019. On the one hand, these projects and initiatives allow us to strengthen our ties with sibling infrastructures like CLARIN and CESSDA, as well as our long-standing European partners like LIBER and Europeana. On the other hand, these are also unique opportunities for the national DARIAH members to work more closely together.

Our activities map largely on to three key strategic areas: building infrastructural components of open Humanities, creating pathways to the open research culture and opening up scholarly communication to cover the entire process of scholarly knowledge creation. Working across these projects and initiatives gives us far more than just a sum of their parts. In addition to gaining the richest possible overview of the European Open Science landscape, and building a role for DARIAH as a knowledge broker across these projects, we also leverage the needs of our stakeholder communities to both expand the Open Science dialogue and create a coherent and focussed presence for ourselves within a busy landscape. Through these projects, we build bridges between local and domain-specific communities of practice and the emerging European Open Scholarship ecosystem.

SSH Open Marketplace

DARIAH's involvement and achievements in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project

As one of the five cluster projects that aim at implementing thematic areas of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), SSHOC started to ground the work that makes EOSC a reality for SSH researchers. In 2019, thanks to the work of three linked DARIAH partners in Austria, Germany and Poland, DARIAH:

- delivered the [system specification of the SSH Open Marketplace](#). Based on an extensive requirements engineering process, the report defines the user requirements, data model, and system architecture for this discovery portal, drawing thus a clearer picture of what is the SSH Open Marketplace and what's in it for researchers.
- participated in key events in order to collect users' inputs – like the research librarians communities during the [LIBER Conference](#) in June 2019 – and to ensure the best integration possible of the SSH Open Marketplace in the EOSC ecosystem (see the poster presented during the [EOSC Symposium](#) in November 2019).
- contributed to enhance the discussion on training materials in the EOSC context by the release of the ["Inventory of existing learning materials"](#) in SSH (coordinated by the Austrian Center for Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage (ACDH-CH), Austrian Academy of Sciences).

ii. Connecting with Our Peers

Open science is not the only issue that inspires us to collaborate closely with our fellow research infrastructures and other umbrella organisations. DARIAH's community and interests cross into a wide variety of domains, giving us access to an exceptionally large and rich set of potential partners for initiatives large and small. Of note in 2019 has been our support for the development of policies and supports for cultural heritage, including the Memorandum of Understanding we signed in June with the Virtual Multimodal Museums Network (ViMM) and our continued contributions to the formation of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) as a partner in the ERIC preparatory project.

Similarly, we partnered with organisations in the course of 2019 in order to expand our outreach to humanities researchers, both through our joint booth at the Association of Digital Humanities Organisations' DH2019 conference in Utrecht (shared with CLARIN and the PARTHENOS project) and our presentation at the 2019 HERA (Humanities in the European Research Area) Conference in Gdansk, Poland.

2. Connecting, Informing, Creating and Fostering

a. Measuring Our Impact

The four pillars of DARIAH's strategy have come into clear focus as we have worked within the productive constraints of the first Strategic Action Plan over the past two years. The aim in 2019 was to make these central to the organisation's strategy as the embodiment of how we add value as a research infrastructure. Managing our resources and our message according to these clear spheres of engagement are a part of that, but measuring our success against them will be a yet larger one.

Evaluating the success of an organisation is a crucial activity, defined also in terms of making progress toward its strategic goals. DARIAH has made great efforts to define a set of indicators that truly capture and measure success based upon a solid understanding of what our stakeholders value. In the early phase of DARIAH's development, success could be easily measured through growth. When new countries would join, that validated our message and our activities.

We continue to plan to expand and grow the number of DARIAH countries, but membership growth alone is not a good measure for DARIAH: what we really want our KPIs to provide evidence for and focus our efforts upon is the depth and richness of our impact into research communities, into national consortia, into the practices and knowledge base of individual researchers who may or may not consider themselves 'digital humanists.'

In this spirit, in 2019 we launched a plan with a number of quantitative and qualitative KPIs, expressed in the form of a Balanced Scorecard covering the areas of Use, Efficiency, Scientific and Community Impact. These indicators will be collected throughout the central European office and national consortia and will be illustrated by Impact Case Studies published annually. For 2019, we would like to give a glimpse of the richness documented in numbers from our national consortia.

b. Connecting Communities

i. Annual Event 2019

The DARIAH Annual Event 2019, which was held on May 15-17 in Warsaw, Poland, was a lively meeting point for researchers, Working Groups, DARIAH related projects and the DARIAH governing bodies to exchange experiences, present progress, explore new ideas and discuss future challenges. This year's event introduced a new format. It combined meetings of DARIAH bodies, and a Marketplace to exchange ideas around new research projects and infrastructural solutions, with an open conference setting hosting papers presentations, ignite talks, workshops and posters from the wider research community.

More than 250 participants gathered in Warsaw to present research or exchange knowledge under the overall theme of the event: Humanities Data. The event aimed to address and discuss various notions around Humanities Data: Is the term rich enough to capture the complexity of Humanities research? Are we talking about big or smart data? The key challenge, as described by the Programme Committee, was to keep a reflexive open discourse about the function of data for specific research questions, and the development of a culture to address the whole spectrum of 'data needs' of humanities scholars across all fields, all forms of collaboration and all societal relevant questions.

The participants had the opportunity to enjoy two keynote lectures by Prof. Sally Wyatt and Dr. Lev Manovich. Sally Wyatt, Professor of Digital Cultures at Maastricht University, gave an opening keynote on "What are we talking about when we talk about data in the humanities?" noting that data as a term may be too flat to capture all the kinds of things that humanities researchers are all dealing with. She also indicated that the use of the word 'data' tends to assume that everything is digital, which is not the case. Dr. Lev Manovich, Professor of Computer Science at The Graduate Center, CUNY and Director of the Cultural Analytics Lab that pioneered analysis of visual culture using computational methods, gave the final keynote on "What does data want" suggesting that *"Many academic disciplines use data science to analyse contemporary culture. The question is: Shall we continue to aggregate big cultural data and reduce it to a small set of patterns? Or shall we refuse this dominant paradigm instead and focus on diversity, variability and differences?"*.

The 2019 Annual Event was one of the biggest for DARIAH, welcoming also many new participants from Polish research centers, universities and libraries, but also early career researchers from all over Europe. A blogging competition that ran ahead of the event gave the opportunity to early career researchers to claim funding, offered by DARIAH, to travel to Warsaw and present their research at the event. Many of the presentations and a book of abstracts are openly accessible and archived on the [DARIAH website](#).

Annual Event (images by Maciej Tarkowski, CC BY)

DESIR Winter School (images by Luisa Seixas, CC BY)

ii. DESIR Winter School 2019

The DESIR Winter School 2019 “Shaping new approaches to data management in arts and humanities” was held in Lisbon on 10-13 of December in the premises of the NOVA University. The event was organised in the context of the Horizon 2020-funded project DESIR (DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined) and was a joint initiative of DARIAH and the Faculty of Social and Human Sciences of the NOVA University Lisbon. During four days of intensive courses, participants got a better insight of best practices to maximise the potential of their scholarly resources and to take practical steps in opening up their research in ethically and legally responsible ways in the digital arts and humanities. The ultimate goal of the Winter School was to strengthen participants’ skills in research data management, curation, sharing, preservation and reuse.

Participants were selected through a competitive call for applications. Overall, the scientific committee received more than 70 applications from all over Europe. Finally, 20 participants with different disciplinary backgrounds and on different career-levels were selected from across Europe, from Belarus to the United Kingdom. Experts from within and beyond the DARIAH community delivered lectures covering a number of crucial topics for data management such as persistent identifiers (PIDs), open research notebooks, humanities data, innovative publishing practices, data management plans, copyright and licensing. Although these topics

are increasingly required to be parts of researchers’ digital skillset and are conditions of access for funding, research data management training is currently not well represented in higher-education curricula. The positive and constructive atmosphere eased the knowledge exchange between experts and participants.

During the event, we realised the need for new professional roles emerging around research data management also in Arts and Humanities domains (data stewards, data managers, Open Science officers etc.) to exchange with each other along the domain-specific dimension. To address this need, as a follow-up of the Winter School, in 2020 we aim to establish a Research Data Management Working Group to create and maintain a brokering hub for both researchers and support staff specialised in research data management in disciplinary contexts from lexicography to archaeology.

The event was a milestone in terms of recording: for the first time, we had the chance to pilot the newly launched event capture functionality on DARIAH-Campus. As a result, [videos, abstracts, slides and community notes have been made available](#) for those who could not attend the event and would like to learn more about new approaches to data management in the arts and humanities.

iii. Final DARIAH Beyond Europe Event

In the context of DESIR, a series of international workshops was organised entitled “DARIAH beyond Europe”. The last workshop of the series took place at the National Library of Australia in Canberra on 27-29 March 2019, in conjunction with the second annual Humanities, Arts and Culture Data Summit. This landmark event, which was organised in collaboration with the [Australian Research Data Commons \(ARDC\)](#) and the [Australian Academy of the Humanities \(AAH\)](#), brought together more than 100 people interested in the future of humanities, arts and cultural research powered by data. This included experienced and emerging researchers, research support communities, national initiatives and representatives of the Australian Government. The event showcased the groundbreaking activities happening across Australia and Europe and the common challenges in data-driven humanities and arts research, digital cultural collections and research infrastructures and opened up potential collaboration opportunities with researchers and institutions. The DARIAH beyond Europe series has not only increased DARIAH's visibility internationally but has led DARIAH to reflect on its long-term approach to its international activities much more deeply.

iv. Helsinki Hackathon DHH 2019

DARIAH together with CLARIN supported the Helsinki Digital Humanities Hackathon (#DHH19) with travel bursaries. The event took place from 15-24 May 2019 and gathered students and researchers of the humanities, social sciences, and computer science. During a week and a half of intensive multi-disciplinary work, the groups applied digital methods to a variety of data sets, with the goal of solving research questions in the following 4 areas:

- The Many Voices of European Parliamentary Debates
- Genre and Style in Early Modern Publications
- Brexit in Transnational Social Media
- Newspapers and Capitalism

The event attracted participants from 14 different countries. “DHH is a concept that we have been developing for more than 5 years,” says Mikko Tolonen, one of the organisers of the Digital Humanities Hackathon. “Last year we mixed international students with local University of Helsinki and Aalto students for the first time.”

DHH-19

“We were quite curious how this will work out because not only are we attempting a project course that is truly multidisciplinary but also international. This year we proved that the idea of going international was fruitful. In 2019, we had 4 excellent groups with interesting results. We are grateful to CLARIN and DARIAH for making this possible”.

Mikko Tolonen

The blogs of the different research groups are [available online](#). More information about DHH19, including the groups' final presentations – video recording, slides, and posters, can be found at the [Helsinki Centre for Digital Humanities website](#).

v. European Summer University in Digital Humanities

With eleven tuition fellowships granted to doctoral students and young scholars from Eastern and Southeastern European Countries, DARIAH was one of the sponsors of the tenth edition of the European Summer University in Digital Humanities held on July 22 – August 2, 2019 at the University of Leipzig.

Under the theme of 'Culture and Technology', the topics of the Summer University varied from XML-TEI based document encoding and Stylometry to Humanities Data and Mapping Environments. By offering a large choice of workshops, lectures, panels, hands-on and poster sessions during eleven days, participants had the opportunity to gain new in-depth knowledge in the area of Humanities Computing and Digital Humanities in the broad sense and to develop their own projects.

Apart from the diversity of represented research topics, cultures and methods highlighted by the funded participants, ESU is considered to be one of the most profound learning events in this domain and a place with extraordinary networking opportunities which lays the foundation of international collaboration. This year ESU continued to foster a broader conversation that welcomed international perspectives on Digital Humanities, including keynote speakers from Brazil, Russia and Cameroon.

Investing more on training and education and especially on providing opportunities to early career researchers, DARIAH liaised with ESU in 2019, to celebrate its tenth edition and to financially support young scholars gain access to a well established and successful learning event. Based on the experience of the good 2019 collaboration and the enthusiastic reports received from the funded scholars, DARIAH will continue its support for the 2020 edition.

"This kind of summer university is even more influential for students coming from countries like Georgia, because we obviously have fewer opportunities to learn about DH or to connect with people as easily as in Central Europe. Also, there is a pragmatic side, in that it is much more expensive for us as we are lacking choices in scholarships. Thus, I want to thank DARIAH-EU (and all the other organisations and foundations that offer scholarships for ESU participants), because it was not only about knowledge and studying. ESU has been a life-changing experience for me." M.M.

vi. DARIAH Code Sprint 2019

As a follow-up of the event that took place in 2018, a second Code Sprint was organised in the context of the Horizon 2020 funded project DESIR (DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined) on 24-26 September 2019 in Berlin at the FORUM Factory. Over the three days, the Code Sprint raised the interest of 17 participants. Once again, it focused on bibliographical metadata to continue the work initiated in DESIR, as part of the first Code Sprint in 2018, for delivering three functional demonstrators in areas that are of central importance for DARIAH's long-term sustainability: entity-based search, scholarly content management and visualisation. Furthermore, the Code Sprint aimed at providing knowledge transfer and training to interested researchers and developers with a Digital Humanities affiliation.

The programme was divided into three different tracks:

Track A: GROBID, a service that allows the extraction of bibliographical data and citations from PDF. This tool, which was successfully built at the first Code Sprint, was further developed during the 2019 Code Sprint inviting participants to enrich GROBID functionalities by adding an acknowledgment parsing service. The goal was to produce a new service for extracting acknowledgement text and formatting the results in XML/TEI or JSON. Information that can be extracted

from the given acknowledgement string is, for example, educational institution, funding agency, grant name, grant number, individual, affiliation of individual, project name, research institution, other institution.

Track B: BibSonomy, a social bookmarking system for researchers. It allows users to bookmark all types of bibliographic data, such as papers, books, articles etc. With its RESTAPI it enables collaborative storage and retrieval of bibliographic metadata. The aim in 2019 was to enrich the tool by adding further features such as:

- Metadata extraction from text files in general, to allow usage of the tool beyond pdf files,
- Implementing a proper login feature for BibSonomy users
- Improved User Interface to allow optimal use of the tool's features
- Open web API for accessing the tool's features.

Track C: VIStory, which enables the visualisation of time dependent graphs of relation. One of the major substantial outcomes of the previous Code Sprint was the novel generic concept of time dependent graphs of relations and its visual presentation. Examples of such graphs may be co-authorship and citation graphs, genealogy trees, or characters interaction graphs. From the visual perspective both the structure and time characteristics of such graphs play a significant analytical role. Within the 2019 Code Sprint, the focus was on the extension of the tool both towards new data formats and use cases, as well as new visual forms. The participants had the opportunity to work on mapping different data to the generic model of graphs and/or on the translation of data formats to intermediate RDF description (subject-predicate-object).

Currently, users can upload a pdf file and have metadata automatically extracted using an integrated version of GROBID. In a further step, users can correct the metadata and save it to BibSonomy. The system also provides information about missing metadata. The results of the Code Sprint are openly available on the DARIAH Github repository for anyone to reuse. All three demonstrators will be made available on a common website, hosted and maintained by CLARIAH-DE.

vii. Promoting and Connecting DARIAH in Europe and Beyond

The DARIAH Coordination Office, the Board of Directors and the members of its various bodies are hosting, organising, presenting, participating and attending various events over the year. From our main DARIAH events, to project meetings, conferences and training workshops, this is a central activity for DARIAH to represent the infrastructure and the arts and humanities as a discipline in various different contexts. Grasp the impact of our 2019 events presence in the map below.

c. Creating Tools and Services for the Community

i. Launch of DARIAH-Campus

In November 2019, as part of the DESIR project, **DARIAH-Campus** was launched following research into best practice for sustainability of training materials among other large projects within the DARIAH community. DARIAH-Campus is a discovery framework and hosting platform for learning resources that offers access to training materials from DARIAH-affiliated projects and partners across Europe.

Currently, DARIAH-Campus offers original hosted resources, links to existing resources from large projects, 'pathfinder' articles providing a review and critique of learning materials around specific themes, and 'captured' events such as the DESIR Winter School. Further resources are currently in development with a view to publication in Spring 2020, and work will continue throughout 2020 to showcase the existing materials already in place and support more contributions from the DARIAH community.

DARIAH-Campus, launched in November 2019

ii. Citizen Science PARTHENOS Module

In early 2019, members of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office began work on a module that investigated the practicalities of conducting citizen science projects in a humanities context for the PARTHENOS project. Entitled 'Citizen Science within the (Digital) Humanities', the module was written by Prof. Jennifer Edmond (President of the Board of Directors, DARIAH-EU), Eliza Papaki (Communications Officer, DARIAH-EU) and Dr. Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra (Open Science Officer, DARIAH-EU), and was edited by Vicky Garnett (then in her capacity as a member of the PARTHENOS project).

The module was launched in June 2019, and featured case studies from DARIAH-affiliated projects and partners, and discussed the set-up, implementation and evaluation of citizen science projects. In October 2019, the module was enhanced further with the inclusion of a series of case study videos featuring two leading researchers from the Transcribe Bentham Project: Prof. Melissa Terras and Dr. Justin Tonra. These videos not only provided valuable insight into the issues that can arise during citizen science projects, such as funding, sustainability, ethics and recruitment, but also ensured a wider audience due to the popularity of the Transcribe Bentham project. These new videos were launched by Prof. Jennifer Edmond at the PARTHENOS project Impact Event held in Rome in early October 2019, and tweets about the launch were shared throughout social media. The module itself has been viewed over 250 times since its launch in June 2019, with an increase in traffic occurring at the time of the launch of these Transcribe Bentham videos.

In terms of use as a training resource, the Citizen Science module has also been used in other training programmes, in particular among the Web2Learn training provisions. In one instance, it was used as one of the pool of citizen science projects that were analysed in the study [Academia permeating society through Citizen Science: Use cases of engagement in Higher Education](#) although it was specifically cited. In addition, the module will be used by Web2Learn in a 4-day workshop organised within the **INOS** team in Bordeaux, in May 2020. This training is for project members and local stakeholders interested in citizen science.

Image source: LERU

iii. Launch of DARIAH Open

Since 2018, we have been actively supporting the DARIAH communities in making their scholarly practices more open via training, workshops, infrastructural support and [DARIAH's Open Access policy](#). A key takeaway from this advocacy work was that there is a strong need for a dedicated platform where scholars can explore and discuss pathways to the open research culture as they specifically pertain to research communities in the arts and humanities. To fulfil this need, in February 2019, we launched the [DARIAH Open blog](#). We use this platform to bring together news, resources, expert interviews, success stories but also debates on discipline-specific challenges from around Open Humanities to explore how the core values of Open Science – such as innovation, transparency, accountability, equity and social-cognitive justice in knowledge production – make sense in our own scholarly practices and in the variety of contexts our work is embedded into. Only by listening to and understanding truly diverse voices can we gain a deeper understanding of the various issues surrounding Open Science in the arts and humanities. To this end, we also highlight achievements coming from the national DARIAH members, such as the ACDH virtual hackathon series. Besides, by launching the DARIAH Open Scholar Stars interview series, we wish to share a range of perspectives and personal experiences of researchers, librarians, and other practitioners with openness to strengthen our communities of practice and to learn how to put things into practice more easily. All the posts are licensed under CC-BY license which means that anyone can freely reuse and build on them. In the first year of DARIAH Open, we were especially glad to see some of the posts taken up and translated by academic communities who had yet no ties to DARIAH.

iv. The DARIAH Theme 2018-19: Strategic Service Sustainability: Evaluation and Impact

This year's funding call, entitled 'Strategic Service Sustainability for DARIAH', focused on the chronic problem of software and tool sustainability in the digital humanities, while also looking forward to the build phase of the Marketplace for data, tools and services. The call attracted a high number of well articulated and competitive applications in the areas of training, standardisation, datasets, geolocation and annotation services, thesauri and vocabularies, among others. All projects concerned existing services or tools with a potentially wide long-term usership and their future sustainability as part of DARIAH's strategy.

The following projects have been funded with an overall budget of 67,305 €:

- **Awareness, understanding and having fun. Fostering communities around the Standardization Survival Kit**

Laurent Romary, Charles Riondet, Sally Chambers, Johan Van der Eycken, Klaus Illmayer, Paul Bertrand, Björn-Olav Dozo, Karlheinz Mörth, Olivier Marlet, Dorian Seillier, Lionel Tadjou (Inria Paris)
- **DARIAHdocs as sustainable collaboration platform**

Peter Gietz (DAASI International GmbH)
- **Digital Humanities Course Registry Sustain – Improving Sustainability through Usability**

Tanja Wissik (Austrian Academy of Sciences)
- **Standard Sustainability: Improving the Usability of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)**

Marjorie Burghart (CNRS-CIHAM UMR 5648)
- **Towards a Sustainable Annotation Tool: Integrating Recogito with DARIAH**

Rebecca Kahn, Leif Isaksen, Rainer Simon, Elton Barker, Valeria Vitale (Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society)
- **#dariahTeach PROTEUS: A Novel Model for Sustaining Peer-Reviewed Open Access Teaching Materials**

Konstantinos Papadopoulos (University of Maastricht)

Focus on the DARIAH Theme project “Awareness, understanding and having fun. Fostering communities around the Standardization Survival Kit”

The [Standardization Survival Kit](#) (SSK) is an overlay platform dedicated to promote a wider use of standards and best practices for the application of digital methods within the Arts and Humanities. It is built around research scenarios, providing contextual information on how standards can be applied in a given research project. Scenarios are living objects that can be improved, reused, rated by the users, which makes the SSK a tool in the hands of its users' community.

The general objective in the project has been to put the technical sustainability of the SSK on track, by creating a long-living and scalable service based upon an active and motivated users' community. Funded by the DARIAH theme call, three face to face meetings in the form of use-case development workshops were organised to add new research scenarios to the SSK. Another outcome of the funding was the creation of digital educational materials and user-friendly documentation: an SSK onboarding cartoon released in April 2019.

Focus on the DARIAH Theme project “Digital Humanities Course Registry Sustain – Improving Sustainability through Usability”

The Digital Humanities Course Registry (DHCR), a joint project of CLARIN and DARIAH, serves as a hub to collect information on DH programmes, courses, lectures and summer schools across Europe (and the world). The regularly updated database contains 208 courses and training events at the moment.

Within the framework of the Theme call, DARIAH funded the “DH Course Registry Sustain” project. The goal was to increase usability and interoperability to improve the overall sustainability. In early December 2019, the revamped design of the DH Course Registry was launched, which is now available under a new URL. At the same time, the API was made publicly available including documentation.

Focus on the DARIAH Theme project “Standard Sustainability: Improving the Usability of the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI)”

This project aimed to address a sustainability threat in the TEI community. While the standard for digital scholarly editions itself is evolving organically in an open and inclusive fashion, the software ecosystem around it does not always follow suit, especially in regard to editors. On the one hand, the community can rely on the long-standing and feature-rich oXygen XML editor, which is the go-to place for any bigger editorial endeavour. On the other hand, oXygen is a commercial product and might not be affordable for everyone, plus, a big full-featured editor is not always the best choice for teaching purposes or smaller projects.

To address this lack of free, open source, TEI-aware editors, the project aimed at making an existing, open-source and cross-platform editor, jEdit, more “TEI-friendly”. To this end, a TEI plug-in was developed for jEdit, written in Java and released under the GNU General Public licence. It embeds the latest version of the TEI schema and stylesheets, offers auto-completion features with tooltips for TEI markups and adds different types of validation and transformations, among other things.

Focus on the DARIAH Theme project “Towards a Sustainable Annotation Tool: Integrating Recogito with DARIAH”

Recogito is an online platform for collaborative semantic annotation of texts and maps. Recogito currently has over 5,000 registered users and between 200 and 1,500 edits per day on average. The grant primarily enabled work on technical developments which embedded Recogito within scholarly practice by establishing it within the DARIAH ecosystem of tools and services (1. technical interoperability); and by working with the DARIAH community, the platform reached better user-community support by creating links with interested institutions and individuals (2. user-community support).

Work has been delivered on simplifying system operations by enhancing the – previously skeletal – administration interfaces (for system maintenance, backup, monitoring, account administration, etc.) and documentation so that Recogito can be set up and operated more easily without the need for assistance from the Pelagios core team.

To address the second issue, the team provided workshops which trained users on how to use Recogito for research and in teaching. Several of these workshops took place, including at the DARIAH Annual Event in Warsaw in May 2019, and at workshops in Vienna and Göttingen. Also, existing informal collaborations with DARIAH Working Groups have been strengthened by embarking on two projects with members of the GeoHumanities Working group aimed at using Pelagios technology for exploring historical sources.

d. Working Groups Funding Scheme 2019-20

DARIAH recognises the strategic role of its Working Groups which represent – according to the Strategic Plan 2019-2026 – one of the four pillars of the DARIAH activities. For this reason, and following the previous scheme 2017-2018, a new funding programme was launched in August 2019, directed only to the DARIAH Working Groups and aimed at supporting their activities. The funded projects are:

1. *WG Digital Urban Heritage – Everyday experiences and heritage in south European cities: Digital tools and practices (5,000 €)*

The project is about the organisation of an intensive hands-on workshop for community building through participatory design and co-creation methodologies which will allow the Working Group to work with local groups and interested in the topic researchers, and to study, discuss and analyse sites of interest in the city of Palermo (Italy).

2. *WG Digital Numismatics + WG Visual Media and Interactivity (joint proposal) – Handling 2D and 3D image-based resources: bringing together IIF & 3D (5,300 €)*

The DARIAH Working Groups Visual Media and Interactivity (VMI) and Digital Numismatics (DN) are cooperating in order to address the challenge on how 2- and 3-dimensional objects are digitally recorded and published. This proposal makes reference to two particular technologies: the International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) as an example of a recently established technology that is now finding widespread application with increasing interest from research H&A communities (Medieval studies, CH, Literature, etc.); and 3D-scanning and modelling, for which a wide variety of technologies and storage formats are being developed, but without significant cross-community cooperation.

3. *WG Geo-Humanities – Learning Spatial Humanities with dariahTeach (5,000 €)*

This project intends to bring members of the DARIAH community with expertise in online learning, geohumanities research and linked open data together for a writing sprint in order to produce a series of learning materials including

syllabi, technical tutorials and complete courses. These materials will form the basis of a collection of freely available resources focussing on innovative digital geo-humanities practices and research methodologies.

4. *WG ELDAH – The DARIAH ELDAH consent form wizard (4,800 €)*

Contemporary ethical conception implies that all research conducted on data collected from human subjects, and more specifically all audio, photo or video recordings involving humans must be accepted by the subjects themselves through the procedure of informed consent. In this project, a “consent form wizard” will be developed which will enable digital scholars and the wider research infrastructure community to quickly and easily obtain a standardised consent form that is based on the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and therefore legally valid in all of the European Union.

5. *DH Course Registry – Reaching out: Dissemination Strategy and Planning for the DH Course Registry (4,762 €)*

Designed as a hub to collect information on DH teaching activities across Europe and beyond and to increase the visibility of these teaching activities beyond the usual university networks, the DH Course Registry (DHCR) is a search environment that allows users to access a database containing, at this point, over 230 courses and training events in Europe and beyond. This project elaborates a strategy in order to benefit from the already existing communication networks (DARIAH, CLARIN) in a planned way and increase the reach of the DH Course Registry and the impact of the Working Group through these channels and campaigns.

In conclusion, the Working Groups funding for the year 2019 has been granted with a total of 24,862 €. The granted projects will run until 31 October 2020.

e. Harnessing our National Networks: In Kind Contributions 2017

In kind contributions have always been at the heart of DARIAH's distributed model for building and maintaining an infrastructure comprised of and serving a large and heterogeneous user base via a similarly large and heterogeneous network of members. While the in-kind mechanism accurately reflects the nature of who we are and what we do, it can be challenging to harness effectively. For this reason, DARIAH undertook a multi-year project to revise its system for the management of contributions, starting already with the inception of the Humanities at Scale project in 2015. First building the tool, then implementing it, collecting contributions and assessing them has taken time, but in 2019 we finally were able to harvest the fruits of these labours.

The 2017 DARIAH contributions, which were submitted in 2018 and assessed in 2018-2019, were as diverse and exciting as ever. With 288 individual entries spanning the 9 major categories foreseen in the reference architecture, they demonstrate both the range of activity in our national nodes and the richness of the services offered across the network.

The contributions highlight DARIAH's deep integration into the national and transnational networks of our users, intersecting, for instance, with connection to three different European COST Networks being submitted via the Netherlands, Greece and Poland. It also illustrates with great clarity the range of interests that are pursued beneath our umbrella, from game play and theory (Denmark) to Portuguese early music (Portugal), and disciplines, from archaeology (Italy) to education (Serbia). The range of types of services is equally broad, with training materials, such as the Ranke2 platform for digital source criticism (Luxembourg) and the DH Course Registry (Austria), sitting alongside more generic user-facing services such as Etherpad (Germany) and large scale scholarly data and knowledge management services like Nakala (France).

With the workflow now proven to manage and quality assure these contributions, we look forward to finding new ways to feature and share them in the future!

In Kind Contributions 2017 – Harnessing Our National Networks

f. Outputs of the DESIR Project

2019 marked the end of the DESIR (DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined) project, funded by the European Commission through the Horizon 2020 programme, which ran from 1 January 2017 until the end of the year. The project was dedicated in strengthening the sustainability of DARIAH and it was designed to address six key dimensions of the infrastructure: dissemination, growth, technology, robustness, trust and education.

Key outputs in 2019

The DESIR project's goal of exploring new sustainability pathways for DARIAH underpinned a large number of the events and activities described throughout this report, from the third "DARIAH beyond Europe" event at the National Library of Australia in Canberra (see page 16) to the DESIR Winter School "Shaping new approaches to data management in arts and humanities", held in Lisbon, Portugal, in December 2019 (see page 15) and the second DARIAH Code Sprint held in Berlin, Germany, in September 2019 (see page 18). Also, as presented in page 8, DARIAH welcomed two new member countries in 2019, thanks to DESIR, Bulgaria and Czech Republic, and made significant progress towards the DARIAH membership in accession countries, welcoming also new Cooperating Partners.

What have we learned from DESIR?

Aiming to establish DARIAH as a sustainable research infrastructure, DESIR delivered extensive research leading to recommendations that will set the basis for future activities within the DARIAH and the research infrastructures landscape more broadly. The full resulting reports are all available in the [DARIAH collection of the HAL repository](#). Some of the key findings from this rich resource were as follows:

Work on trustworthiness and recognition of DARIAH was led by the NOVA School of Social Sciences and Humanities, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, resulting in over 60 recommendations that comprise the '[Recommendations & Community Engagement Virtual Tool](#)'. Building upon initial survey findings that discovered that recognition of DARIAH's services was generally lower than expected outside of small national coordination cohorts, this tool brings specific measures DARIAH can implement in order to promote research excellence, ensure integration, foster collaborative learning and strengthen DARIAH's representation in European and international policy arena.

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DESIR (image by Matija Dronjić, CC BY)

Another important stream of work in DESIR dedicated in exploring the role Research Infrastructures such as DARIAH can play in the **European educational landscape** by complementing rather than replacing the pedagogical models prevalent in HEIs today. This work, led by the Belgrade Centre for Digital Humanities, found that there was a significant opportunity forming for DARIAH to take a more prominent role in the development and dissemination of early-career researchers' transferable skills and competences, working more closely with higher education institutions to deliver alignment with the findings of the 2018 Eurodoc report.

Another important area of work delivered within the project, led by the University of Göttingen, was a set of generic guidelines of **workflow for new services** that support individual research as well as new research projects, contributing also to their future sustainability. This generic model built upon a gap analysis to design and demonstrate across four service case studies (described under the section on the DARIAH Code Sprint above) a reusable workflow by which DARIAH might identify and stream the development of key infrastructural components.

The process of strengthening DARIAH's sustainability could only be achieved if we really understand the surrounding landscape. A **deep investigation on how we see ourselves** was conducted in the course of the project by closely examining the structure and governance of our fellow organisations. By comparing

DARIAH's structure and function with a diverse and thought-provoking set of comparators, including Europeana, the BBC, LIBER and BBMRI (a research infrastructure for biomedical sciences), the study was able to put into clear relief the unique strengths DARIAH had developed in its policy work and mechanism of the working groups, while also indicating room for further refinement in how we interact with our wider group of stakeholders and present a clear service orientation.

This last point was further explored in the **Business Plan** and Marketing Strategy work of the project. Based on the in-depth analysis of DARIAH's Financial and Funding Framework, DARIAH's business model suggests that its sustainability lies in five main categories: Contributions of Members, European and international project grants, National and local grants, Commercial activities and Individual and corporate contributions. All of these categories were analysed in the context of a five-year financial plan, ensuring that DARIAH's operations will continue with the highest quality standards and will meet the expectations of the arts and humanities research communities.

All these lessons learned are openly available and will hopefully be a source for knowledge and inspiration for fellow researchers and organisations aiming for sustainability, financial viability and community trust.

3. Doing Things Right and Doing the Right Things

a. Changes in the Organisation

2019, in contrast to the previous year which saw many changes in the DARIAH team, can be described as a year of stability and consolidation. While Sonja de Leeuw (Utrecht University), stepped down from the Scientific Board in March after her retirement without being replaced, two new positions were created within the DARIAH Coordination Office (DCO) in 2019, to support two of the four strategic pillars: the Marketplace and Training & Education. First, Laure Barbot was recruited in January 2019 to lead and coordinate the participation of DARIAH and of its partners in the European project SSHOC, in which the Marketplace is being developed under DARIAH's leadership. A couple of weeks later, DARIAH hired a Training and Education officer, Deborah Thorpe in order to develop its training offer and program, an essential component of its new strategy. Although she was recruited by another institution at the end of the summer, she was fortunately replaced in November by Vicky Garnett who proved to be a welcome addition to the team. Last but not least, the end of 2019 marked the departure of Suzanne Dumouchel, who had worked for several years at DARIAH within the DCO, carrying out many roles: communication, strategic development, relations with research institutions and infrastructures,

etc. She will nevertheless remain in close contact with DARIAH as she has been hired by Huma-Num in Paris, a long-standing partner of DARIAH.

b. Policy Developments

i. DARIAH Publishes a Strategic Plan for 2019-2026

One of the most significant milestones for DARIAH as an organisation in 2019 has been the publication of our first Strategic Plan. The Plan was a result of nearly two years of consultation about who we are as an organisation, and who we want to become; who our users are; how we make an impact on research; and how we can best focus our attentions and resources to realise our **mission** to empower research communities with digital methods to create, connect and share knowledge about culture and society and promote our **vision** that the Arts and Humanities be anchored at the centre of a technologically evolving knowledge society.

The DARIAH Strategic Plan 2019-2026 focuses on four areas of activity around which we will consolidate our activity over the period of the plan:

CREATING: Build a marketplace to facilitate a fluid exchange of tools, services, data and knowledge

TRANSFORMING: Build access to education and training

CONNECTING: Build Working Groups, Hubs and other forms of Transnational and Transdisciplinary organisation

COMPLEMENTING: Build bridges between research policy and communities of practice

DARIAH's Four Strategic Pillars

Achievement of the ambitions of the Strategic Plan will be supported by another DARIAH internal policy instrument developed within 2019, namely the Second Strategic Action Plan (STRAPL). STRAPL I had been a key guiding force for the organisation from the time of its inception in 2017, and the process of delivering upon the challenges it contained was essential to the eventual shape and thrust of the Strategic Plan. But a plan is only as good as its execution, and the complementary time horizons (2-3 years versus 7) and granularity (operational and action-oriented rather than vision and concept-oriented) of the two documents convinced the DARIAH leadership that the focus and guidance the STRAPL provided would still be useful.

In developing our second STRAPL, we refined our concept of how to best create actions, framing them around clear challenges, teams to address them, time horizons for progress and clear assessment methodology. In its second iteration, the STRAPL II has a stronger focus than its predecessor, (with 16 actions rather than 24) and a clear alignment to the Strategic Plan, but continues to challenge us to improve and reflect on our practices of infrastructure provision. Already in the course of 2019 it has inspired us to build the DARIAH-Campus platform, re-imagine our interaction with the arts research community, design a potentially transformational shift in our approach to services and create a well-honed approach to monitoring our performance and impact.

Progress to date on the DARIAH Second Strategic Action Plan (as of 31 December 2019)

Total number of Actions	Total percentage complete	Total months of the current STRAPL	Total percentage of time remaining
16	48%	36	75%

The process of defining and agreeing the new Strategic Action Plan brought a great surge of energy to the activities of DARIAH in the course of 2019. Achievements such as the launch of DARIAH-Campus, agreement of a strong new framework for the governance of the Working Groups, and a proposal to launch a 2020 DARIAH Theme call to engage the arts research community are all tangible outcomes of how our work is being guided by this key document.

The last of these developments deserves particular attention, as the development and implementation of a structured, standardised approach to performance assessment for DARIAH was another hugely ambitious project delivered within 2019. Inspired by the work of the European Commission's High Level Expert Group exploring key performance indicators for research indicators, but also by the values of our community and stakeholders, DARIAH has now adopted a Balanced Scorecard (BSC) approach to its self-assessment.

The BSC will deliver an overall view of DARIAH's health as an organisation by three different lenses through which our performance can be viewed: Access and Use; Efficiency and Effectiveness; and Impact.

Collecting data that is representative and robust will be a challenge, but this Annual Report gives already a first indication of how the BSC will provide us with both a simple and compelling tool for communicating about DARIAH, as well as a valuable tool for helping us to hone operations and strategy into the future.

ii. Working Groups Policy Statement 2019

The foundation of Working Groups as a means of fostering collaboration inside of DARIAH and developing and implementing certain needs and functions for DARIAH has been discussed as early as 2014, and has led to a first policy document published in 2015 with procedures on how to apply, accredit and run a Working Group. Since, running a Working Group has been fully embraced and, as the Report of Working Groups in 2016 showed, a variety of Working Groups emerged, operating in a spectrum from the coordination of specific research communities to addressing DARIAH wide, cross domain questions of technological, communicative and legal-ethical nature.

Working Groups represent autonomous, innovative self-organising processes inside the ERIC. The platform for Working Groups is both firm (in its principles) and open (in the execution of those principles), and represents a form of open cultural innovation. The dynamics of Working Groups and their central place in the [DARIAH Strategy](#) required to re-think their position inside of DARIAH. This includes the relationship between Working Groups and the DARIAH bodies of JRC (Joint Research Committee) and VCC (Virtual Competence Centres), what DARIAH can offer to its Working Groups and what it requires from them. The [Working Group Policy Statement](#), published in 2019, summarises a two-year long discussion process through all DARIAH bodies and addresses all those points, including an alignment to the DARIAH Statutes, the DARIAH Strategy, and the Internal Rules of Procedures.

c. Launch of DARIAH Communications Group

Over the course of 2019, DARIAH moved a step ahead implementing some of the groundwork laid out in 2018 in the context of fostering better communications within the network. Having as aim to achieve a good level of information exchange within and outside the network, especially due to the size, complexity and distributed nature of DARIAH, in 2019 we launched the DARIAH Communications Group, inviting communications specialists and researchers dealing with the tasks of communication from all member countries and Cooperating Partners to join.

The aim of this initiative, which is a long standing practice also in other ERICs, was to create a network of professionals to keep up-to-date with news happening at the national, institutional and European level, but also for knowledge exchange of best practices and support in various communications tasks.

The group, which currently has 17 members, convened virtually every month having as agenda to streamline the information flow between the members, brainstorm on new communication ideas to reach out more efficiently to new audience, rethink the communication channels and introduce new ones where appropriate and map the DARIAH user audience to develop a better understanding of their various needs. In preparation of launching this initiative, the Outreach and Communications Officer leading the group, Eliza Papaki, collaborated with the Communications Officers of other ERIC's running similar groups (CLARIN, CESSDA and CERIC ERICs) to draw on experience, exchange best practices and interesting agenda items. The launch of the DARIAH Communications Group is one of the steps implemented in 2019 for sustaining on the one hand a good communication level for DARIAH, to rethink and innovate on the other hand and foster a more well-connected network.

d. Strategy Days 2019

The year 2019 opened for the third year in a row with the now established Strategy Days. These three days of work and exchange are an opportunity for the members of the various governing bodies – Board of Directors, Senior Management Team, Coordination Office and Joint Research Committee – to draft, discuss and develop the main strategic outlines of DARIAH ERIC for the years to come. For the first time, the National Coordinators were invited as well, thus bringing together all the operational and coordination bodies in order to broaden the consultation process and address a wide range of topics.

The agenda for the Strategy Days was constructed around plenary discussions and breakout sessions. The first ones aimed at discussing global strategic documents – the Strategic Plan or the second version of the Strategic Action Plan – and milestones of the DARIAH activities such as the Annual Event. The second breakout sessions were designed, on the one hand, to address specific strategy-related issues in smaller groups such as communication, performance assessment, internationalisation or partnerships, and, on the other hand, to review the work that has been done within the four strategic pillars while proposing possible directions for development and improvement.

The discussions and conclusions from those Strategy Days led to the finalisation of the [Strategic Plan 2019-2026](#) that was officially approved by the General Assembly in May, but most importantly proved an excellent foundation for the creation of the DARIAH Strategic Action Plan II (2019-2022), succeeding the first one established for the period 2017-2019. It identifies a series of concrete actions to be carried out in order to achieve the major objectives set by the Strategic Plan. For each action, a team and a timeline have been set out so that progress can be monitored regularly and possibly readjusted by the Board of Directors. The Strategic Action Plan II has been reviewed and accepted by the General Assembly in November. This 3-day meeting was an excellent opportunity for all DARIAH internal stakeholders to contribute and agree on a solid strategic basis for the coming years.

4. Looking Ahead

It was on the very last day of 2019 that the Chinese government alerted the World Health Organisation to the discovery of an unusual pneumonia in the province of Hubei. Little did we in the DARIAH community know as we closed out 2019 that we would be finalising our Annual Report for that year under conditions we never would have imagined even a few weeks earlier.

DARIAH was perhaps better prepared for the disruptions of 2020 than many organisations: our team and practices are already highly distributed, electronic and very often virtual, and our explicit meta-level focus on the practices as well as the products of our users as well as ourselves makes us perhaps more able to pivot those practices when circumstances require. None of this can fully protect us from the intrusion of COVID19, however, as we see (at the very least) so many more of our interactions, in Working Groups, projects and in the DARIAH central functions, move to on-line spaces and platforms.

No one knows what normalcy will look like by the end of 2020, nor when that now much longed-for state will be available to any of us. But what we do know is that in these times of upheaval, stable and fit-to-purpose infrastructure, open science practices to connect us, and creative, community-based responses to the myriad challenges we face are the things that will keep research alive. Whatever 2020 brings, DARIAH will use this year to redouble our commitment to being a service and support to the arts and humanities research community, and to ensuring that the dark days of this pandemic are remembered not just as a time of economic plans and biomedical research, but of stories that will need to be told and histories that will need to be gathered, of images that inform us and arts that sustain us.

Appendix I: Administrative and Legal Details

Organisational Chart

Who's Who in DARIAH

Body: Board of Directors

Role: The Board of Directors is the executive body of DARIAH ERIC and its legal representative. It is composed of three directors, appointed by the General Assembly. The BoD provides leadership, represents DARIAH, shapes strategy and controls the performance and is responsible for the day-to-day operations, in support by the DARIAH Coordination Office.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH	Affiliation
Jennifer Edmond	Director	Trinity College Dublin
Frank Fischer	Director	Higher School of Economics, Moscow
Toma Tasovac	Director	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities

Body: Scientific Board

Role: The Scientific Board advises DARIAH, via the General Assembly, on specific issues, such as the future research landscape and technological innovation. Its members are arts and humanities researchers with international reputation in the field and therefore significant experience in digitally enabled research methods.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH/ Affiliation
Riccardo Pozzo	Chair of the Scientific Advisory Board/Università di Verona
Sarah Kenderdine	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL)
Roxane Wyns	LIBIS
Jan Rybicki	Jagiellonian University
Sonja de Leeuw	Utrecht University
Patrik Svensson	UCLA
Jane Ohlmeyer	Trinity College, Dublin
Chad Gaffield	University of Ottawa
Francis Prost	University Paris 1-Panthéon Sorbonne/CNRS/ French Ministry of Higher Education and Research
Arianna Betti	University of Amsterdam

Body: DARIAH Coordination Office

Role: The daily work of DARIAH-EU is undertaken by the DCO; headed by the Secretary General, assisted by the Chief Coordination Officer, it is responsible for financial, legal, coordination and communications operations in respect of all the above bodies for the effective running of the ERIC. It has distributed operations and offices in France (Paris), Germany (Berlin), Ireland (Dublin) and the Netherlands (The Hague).

People

Name	Role in DARIAH
	Arnaud Roi Secretary General
	Anne Grésillon Chief Organisation Officer
	Suzanne Dumouchel Partnerships and Public Affairs Officer
	Marco Raciti European Project Manager
	Erzsébet Tóth-Czifra Open Science Officer
	Yoann Moranville Developer and Research Associate
	Laure Barbot European Project Officer
	Eliza Papaki Outreach and Communications Officer
	Vicky Garnett Training and Education Officer
	Andrea Scharnhorst Chief Integration Officer
	Francesca Morselli Integration Officer
	Femmy Admiraal Integration Officer

Body: National Coordinators Committee

Role: Each DARIAH Member Country has its own National Coordinator, who oversees DARIAH activities in his or her country on behalf of its national membership consortium. These activities are the setting up of a national road map for the digitally enabled arts and humanities, and coordinating the submission of in-kind contributions, such as the tools, services, software, collections, expertise and researcher networks that are established as a result of implementing the respective national road map. The NCC meets regularly to integrate national DARIAH activities at the European level.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH/Country	Affiliation
Sally Chambers	Chair of the National Coordinators Committee/ Belgium	Ghent Centre for Digital Humanities
Nicolas Larousse	Vice Chair of the National Coordinators Committee/ France	Huma Num
Mörth Karlheinz	Austria	Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, Austrian Academy of Sciences
Walter Scholger	Austria	Center for Information Modeling – Austrian Centre for Digital Humanities, University of Graz
Dimitar Iliev	Bulgaria	Sofia University
Kiril Simov	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Koraljka Kuzman Šlogar	Croatia	Archive, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology
Martin Lhoták	Czech Republic	Czech Academy of Sciences
Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard	Denmark	Digital Humanities Lab Denmark
Mirjam Blümm	Germany	State and University Library Göttingen
Nanette Reißler-Pipka	Germany	Göttingen State and University Library
Maria Spiliotopoulou	Greece	Academy of Athens
Orla Murphy	Ireland	University College Cork
Emiliano Degl'Innocenti	Italy	Italian Council of Research
Andreas Fickers	Luxembourg	Luxembourg Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Gertjan Filarski	Netherlands	KNAW – Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
Jakub Szprot	Poland	ICM, University of Warsaw
Amelia Aguiar Andrade	Portugal	NOVA FCSH
Snežana Petrović	Serbia	Serbian Academy for Sciences and Arts
Jurij Hadalin	Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History/ Primorska University

Body: Joint Research Committee

Role: The JRC organises the integration of DARIAH's technical developments and innovation activities. It is chaired by DARIAH's Chief Integration Officer (CIO) and consists of the Heads of each of DARIAH's Virtual Competency Centres.

People

Name	Role in DARIAH	Affiliation
Andrea Scharnhorst	Chief Integration Officer	DARIAH/DANS
Adeline Joffres	JRC Member	TGIR Huma-Num (CNRS)
Tibor Kálmán	Heads of VCC1	GWDG
Matej Durco		ACDH-OeAW
Agiatis Benardou	Heads of VCC2	Digital Curation Unit, ATHENA R.C.
Marianne Ping Huang		Aarhus University
Georgios Artopoulos	Heads of VCC3	STARC, Cyprus Institute
Tomasz Parkola		Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center
Fabio Cotti	Heads of VCC4	University of Roma Tor Vergata
Dirk Wintergrün		Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

Appendix II: Finances

DARIAH ERIC consists of 19 Member countries that contribute to its budget in two different ways: through cash contributions and in-kind contributions. In 2019, according to the budget voted by the General Assembly, the contributions from the member countries amount to:

2019 total cash contribution	710,153 €
2019 total in-kind contribution	4,263,580 €

It is to be noted that the finances 2019 presented in this report have not been audited yet, since the General Assembly will only meet in November 2019 to validate the accounts. Besides, the last report of the auditor for the year 2018 concluded that DARIAH's financial statements "give a true and fair view of the assets and liabilities and of the financial position and of the net assets of its operation according to the French accounting principles."

However, DARIAH is in position to give an accurate situation of the 2019 finances that reflect DARIAH's operations in an understandable manner for its stakeholders. It is important to clarify that in this first section, only the resources and expenses of DARIAH – without European and other projects – are accounted for.

Resources

Due to their very nature, the in-kind contributions are not included in the calculation of resources available to run DARIAH's operations. The total income 2019 is mostly composed of cash contributions and diverse reimbursements, such as individual participation to the social dinner during DARIAH's annual event or refund for overpayment.

DARIAH balance 2018	460,986 €
DARIAH income 2019	716,234 €
DARIAH expenses 2019	684,458 €
Balance 2019	31,776 €
Total balance	492,762 €

Expenses

The largest component of operating expenses is by far the personnel costs which represents 65% of the total costs. The operational costs for the year 2019 are distributed as follows:

Type of Costs	2019
staff costs	444,756 €
project funding (community and working groups)	72,574 €
travel & accommodation	47,973 €
communication	29,605 €
development in-kind contribution tool	25,000 €
accounting & audit	16,680 €
catering	12,584 €
legal council	12,363 €
financial support to partner events	9,453 €
consulting	7,500 €
consumables	2,231 €
bank charges	1,817 €
conference/membership fee	1,815 €
event organisation	87 €
petty cash	20 €
training	– €
Total	684,458 €

+ diagram costs including staff details

Staff Costs – administration	FTE	Staff Costs – support for the community	FTE
Directors	1.5	Communication officer	1
Secretary-General	1	Developer/technical support	1
Legal and administration officer	1	Policy and partnership	0.5
European project officer	1	Training and education officer	0.7
		Open Science officer	1
		Working group coordinators and experts for in-kind contributions	1

European Projects

European projects funding is solely used to carry out specific projects in which DARIAH is involved in:

- DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined (DESIR), Grant agreement number 731081. The project ended on 31.12.2019
- Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimisation and Synergies (PARTHENOS), Grant agreement number 65419. The project ended on 31.10.2019
- High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure (HIRMEOS), Grant agreement number 731102. The project ended on 30.06.2019
- OpenAIRE Advancing Open Scholarship (OpenAIRE Advance), Grant agreement number 777541.
- The European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science Preparatory Phase (E-RIHS PP), Grant agreement number 739503.
- The Social Sciences & Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC), Grant agreement number 823782
- The ERIC Forum Implementation project (ERIC Forum), Grant agreement number 823798
- Preparing open access in the European research area through scholarly communication (OPERAS-P), Grant agreement number 871069
- Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration (TRIPLE), Grant agreement number 863420

The table below includes personnel as well as other direct costs, such as travel expenses or events organisation:

	Income	Expenses
DESIR	168,910 €	168,910 €
PARTHENOS	32,152 €	32,152 €
HIRMEOS	16,351 €	16,351 €
SSHOC	36,517 €	36,517 €
TRIPLE	2,421 €	2,421 €
OPERAS P	6,942 €	6,942 €
OpenAIRE Advance	11,332 €	11,332 €
ERIC Forum	819 €	819 €
E-RIHS PP	29,359 €	29,359 €
Total European projects	304,802 €	304,802 €

Other Project

DARIAH received in 2018 a total of 50,000 €, 25,000 € from the French Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation (MESRI) and 25,000 € from the German Ministry of Higher Education and Research (BMBF), to organise specific events. On the 50,000 € received in 2018, only 37,413 € remained at the beginning of 2019:

	Income	Expenses
1 event organised end 2018 + 1 to be organised in 2020	37,413 €	10,413 €

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